

what do lichens look for in a substrate?

flakey

Smooth, rough, soft, hard, stable, flakey. These are all textures that differentiate substrates; the physical structural qualities of the surface. Tips of branches, deep grooves in bark, rock texture, and sunlight all also play a role.

texture

smooth

chemistry

The different trace elements, compounds, and minerals are the chemical makeup of a surface. These also affect the pH (acidity) of the material. Different types of tree bark and stones have different pH levels.

Different species of lichens prefer different moisture levels. How a substrate absorbs and retains water is a key factor for which species will grow where. One example is sandstone holds more water than granite.

moisture

what are substrates?

Substrates are what lichens grow on! The things they call home. The three broad categories for substrates are Wood, Rock, and Ground. This pamphlet covers the specifics about the substrates within those categories.

what does substrate matter?

Lichens are attached to substrates so they do not fall off or blow away. They have preferences on where they grow though! Each species is usually found on only one type of substrate. It's important to know what substrate you're looking at to correctly identify what species it is!

substrates that lichens grow on

by
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Corticolous:
Growing
on bark.

trunks

trees: top
to bottom

The different parts of a tree all have their own unique qualities that different species can take advantage of; twigs may have less surface area with more sunlight and the base of a big tree may be shady and moist.

twigs

type
of tree

Different tree species have differences in bark texture, bark acidity, etc. The two broad categories of hardwoods and conifers are both equally suitable for lichens, but host different communities of species.

non-calcareous
rock

sandstone

Non-calcareous rocks lack calcium-carbonate and host a different set of species than calcareous rocks. **Granite** is the most well known example. This also includes silicious rocks; rocks with a high percent of silica such as **sandstone**.

Saxicolous:
growing on
concrete, stone,
rock, pebbles
or brick.

calcareous
rock

granite

Calcium-carbonate is what defines calcareous rock. Many species only grow on calcareous rocks. **Limestone, marble and cement** are the most common calcareous substrates.

concrete

marble

misc. and
human-made
substrates

Some species of lichens are not picky. They will grow on anything that sits still long enough, including human made surfaces. Look for lichens on metal, plastic, and fabric.

fabric

metal

soil

Some lichens species specialize on other natural surfaces. Growing right on soil, sand, moss and liverworts is common; while lichens that grow on leaves are found in tropical or extremely humid environments.

Terricolous:
growing
on soil.

